

DIGITAL PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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SUMMARY

Becoming a central element of the development of public administration, e-government generates opportunities but also challenges. How does e-government relate to public administration? E-government exerts a significant impact on the changing public administration, on the way the public service works, adding new concepts and methods and changing the relations between administrations and citizens.

Keywords: electronic government, public administration, participation, transparency, interactivity, accessibility.

The contemporary world, characterized by the constant development of tools and spaces for accessing information, imposes a sustained pace of adaptation and updating in any field. Public administration is also adapting to change in order to optimize its services and maintain an efficient dialogue with citizens, adopting new technologies. "Today, digital public services are commonly produced by national, state or local authorities and are provided to citizens, businesses and other entities under their jurisdiction." [J. Bertot, E. Estevez, T. Janowski, 2016]

Why e-government?

The expansion of successful e-government implementation means ease in using government services for citizens, improvement in the provision of government services by public authorities, simplification of citizens' compliance with government laws, improvement of citizen engagement and the level of trust in public administrations, reduction of fraud and improvement of financial and time cost efficiency for both citizens and administrations. Electronic governance contributes to raising living standards and becomes a vital tool for governments and their citizens, generating benefits for governments, citizens, and all other stakeholders. The presentation of the concept of electronic governance comes as an answer to the question "What is e-government?", offered in a broader sense than simply using Information Technology in Public Administration. In 2019, UNESCO defined electronic governance: "The use by the public sector of information and communication technologies [ICT] with the aim of improving the provision

of information and services, encouraging citizen participation in the decision-making process and making government more accountable, transparent and efficient." Melitski [2019] extended the definition, arguing that "e-government consists of internet-based innovations that improve citizens' access to government information... services, and ultimately, equitable participation in governance."

Electronic governance represents the provision of government services and activities through digital technology, to increase efficiency, transparency and citizen participation. [United Nations Development Programme, 2020]. "Electronic governance represents the use of digital technologies and data to improve the delivery of public services and increase government efficiency, transparency and accountability, as well as to increase citizen participation in the decision-making process" [European Commission, 2021].

"The concept of digital governance represents a fundamental shift in how governments around the world embrace their mission" [World Bank, 2023]. The same institution defines e-government as "the use of information technology by government agencies that are responsible for transmitting information between people, institutions and all other interested government parties." "E-Government involves new leadership styles, new ways of debating and deciding policies and investments, new ways of accessing education, new ways of listening to citizens and new ways of organizing and providing information and services. The idea of adopting ICT is to go beyond the passive provision of information to the active involvement of citizens in the decision-making process." [UNESCO, 2023]

Electronic governance responds to many challenges facing Public Administration, which is why developing tools to serve citizen-government interaction is essential for both governments and citizens. In the public sector, the goal is for citizens to always be able to reach government agencies through the web and be served by it [Goldkuhl, 2007, p.135].

From purpose to beneficiaries

Developed to fulfill at least two purposes, electronic services can benefit: first, service providers (public administrations) through the automation of part of the administrative task, thus they can accelerate services, resulting in cost reduction; second, service users (businesses and citizens) can benefit, interacting with public authorities, which are then able to respond to needs and requirements at any time, quickly, cheaply and easily. [Vassilakis et al., 2005]. Exposing the

benefits generated by the automation of administrative tasks (significant cost reduction, submission of applications or reports, obtaining information about services offered by public administration, or receiving relevant notifications and updates) is almost no longer necessary, a fact already felt: citizens and public administrations can interact in real time, which has led to closer collaboration, better communication and improved services. Technologies continue to change the way citizens receive information from authorities and communicate with them, "the internet thus contributes to a more diverse and pluralistic media landscape." [Chadwick, 2009a]. To effectively change citizen-government relations, public administration must honor citizens' values and priorities by demonstrating that it listens to citizens and acts on what it hears. [Mark A. Glaser, Robert B. Denhardt, 2000].

Digital public administration, challenges and opportunities

Precisely in its attempt to honor citizens' values and priorities, public administration becomes digital public administration, adapting its administrative processes with the aim of increasing their efficiency, transparency and accessibility. Digital public administration is an important opportunity for governments to improve their services offered and reduce administrative costs, but this comes with its own challenges. While government organizations continue to invest in e-government systems, there are still uncertainties regarding the benefits that can be generated. Without clear expectations, public administrations will not be able to measure and evaluate results. "A Systematic Literature Review of Empirical Research on the Impacts of e-Government: A Public Value Perspective" [MacLean, D. and Titah, R., 2022] through an analysis of 60 empirical studies on the impact of electronic governance in public administration, presents a classification using public value theory according to the role for which value is generated, then according to the nature of the impact on citizens. Impacts are associated here with three roles played by the public: citizen, client and taxpayer. The study results show that the most frequently researched impact is citizen benefit, satisfaction, service quality and improvement in the level of trust and communication for citizens. The same study delimits impact into immediate and indirect impact, which must be taken into consideration by public administrations when making the decision to implement e-government. The research was based on a series of theories and only 26 of them did not use any theory, and 9 compared electronic

governance systems and governments, but all targeted e-government systems from 22 different jurisdictions, most of them from Asia and Europe.

The data collection methods were case studies, followed by secondary sources. Most articles in the sample included a statistical test of the relationship between an antecedent factor and impact, testing 156 different combinations among factors that include characteristics of the government providing the service, the e-government system, system elements and its use. Some research tested interactions of antecedent factors or tested a mediated relationship when one of the antecedent factors had an indirect effect through an outcome.

The study results indicate that the most frequently tested antecedent factors were characteristics of the e-government system (e.g., information quality and ease of use) and characteristics of the use of these systems (e.g., frequency of use and used/not used). The most frequently tested dependent variables were customer satisfaction and trust in government, which fall into the categories of productivity and citizen-government relationship impact respectively. Only two studies researched the effects of government agency characteristics (IT management capacity and service management capacity) on the data quality of that organization. One study examined the effects on an aspect of the service (information provision or transaction processing); this factor was analyzed in combination with a characteristic of the e-government system. Only a few studies analyzed how impacts are interconnected (e.g., how increased customer satisfaction can lead to higher levels of trust in government). There were no articles that researched the impact on the public as taxpayer. No effects were observed on planning, emphasis on quantitative criteria, health/safety/welfare, job satisfaction or protection of rights. Certain impact categories can be associated with multiple roles, especially impact on productivity and the citizen-government relationship. The majority of identified impacts were positive or neutral, only three negative impacts: simplification of jobs for government employees, a reduction in the personal relationship between clients and frontline employees in public administrations and a reduction in confidence in the adequacy of the decision. The most frequently mentioned impact is increased productivity, which can benefit clients and taxpayers. For clients, 18 articles identified increased satisfaction as a result of using e-government services, benefits of reduced costs and time allocated through service use. Performance improvement was the result of 2 studies where the client is an organization, not an individual. Another 15 articles described productivity gains of government institutions (from which the

public benefits as taxpayers) in terms of greater efficiency and speed of service delivery with reduced operating costs.

The second most frequently identified result of e-government implementation is the improvement of the citizen-government relationship, for both citizen and client roles. E-government systems can increase citizens' trust in government or beliefs about government credibility. The articles did not target e-democracy and e-participation systems; however, the results indicate that e-government improves citizens' participation and involvement in public administration policies.

Challenges Vs Opportunities

But it is precisely this participation and involvement in the relationship between citizens and digitalized public administration that encounters numerous challenges. Accessibility: not all citizens have access to technology or do not have the necessary knowledge to access digital services; Data security: Governments must take adequate security measures to protect personal data and sensitive information that could be compromised and used in an unauthorized manner; Implementing technologies in public administration can be difficult and costly due to factors such as existing infrastructure and the technical capabilities of staff; Nevertheless, digital public administration offers numerous opportunities for governments and citizens: Efficiency, through reducing time and costs associated with administrative processes; Transparency of public administration, through providing information and data in real time, which helps citizens better understand how public administration works and leads to active involvement in the decision-making process; Citizen participation, through digital platforms, through which citizens can make suggestions, submit petitions and contribute to the development of public policies; Reduction of bureaucracy: Implementation of digital public administration can contribute to reducing bureaucracy through the elimination of some administrative procedures and/or simplification; Increasing the quality of public services, through increasing efficiency and transparency, as well as through reducing delays and human errors.

Limitations

The results of different research in the field highlight limitations of electronic governance, the most important referring to digital divides: lack of accessibility for important parts of the

population and/or lack of digital skills. The lack of clear expectations of implementation generates the impossibility of measuring and evaluating the results of public administration digitalization.

Conclusions

Digital public administration represents an important opportunity for governments to improve the public services offered and reduce administrative costs. However, digitalization implementation can be difficult and comes with its own challenges. Accessibility, data security and implementation are just some of the challenges facing governments. At the same time, efficiency, transparency, citizen participation, reduction of bureaucracy and increasing the quality of public services are important opportunities for which governments continue to invest in addressing the challenges associated with digitalized public administration.

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